

Modelling of Uncertainty in Geo Sciences Sites

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Abstract. This paper discusses a use cases of dealing with and modelling vague and uncertain geo-references (findspots) based on literature as LOD from the geosciences domain.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) ash airfall in Central Europe, was derived from a Late Pleistocene volcanic event in the Campania region [5, 1]. Around 40,000 yr b2k, the largest eruption of the CI took place in the Phlegraean Fields (Fig. 1). Based on this, massive glass deposits from the CI-eruption covered large parts of the eastern European continent (Fig. 2); volcanic material of the CI is often found in isolated watersheds and valleys. These findspots are recorded in several papers, e.g. ...

- (a) precise coordinates, e.g. "[...] Lago Grande di Monticchio in southern Italy (40°56'N, 15°35'E)" [3]
- (b) references to cities, e.g. Naples [11]
- (c) or references to regions, e.g. Altopiano delle Murge [8] or Castelvita Cave [6]. One of these findspots is "the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River." [7].

Figure 1: Graphic of deposit dispersal during the Campanian Ignimbrite Eruption 40,000 years ago based on [10]. Wikirictor, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

Figure 2: Sample of Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots based on several literature. Florian Thiery and Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0.

2 EXEMPLARY LIST OF CI FINDSPOTS

CI localities can be found in Campania and it's surroundings. The localities are sorted alphabetically; small regions are grouped together.

id	label	wkt	literature
1	Acerra Sink	POINT(14.3624 40.9489)	Scandone et al., 1991
2	Acqua Fidia	POINT(14.6983 40.9285)	Rosi et al., 1999
3	Capezzano	POINT(14.7680 40.7119)	Rosi et al., 1999
4	Casola	POINT(14.5259 40.6993)	Rosi et al., 1999
5	Castelcivita Cave	POINT(15.2092 40.4956)	Fedele et al., 2008;Giaccio et al., 2008
6	Copечchia	POINT(14.7662 40.7198)	Rosi et al., 1999
7	Cuma	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	Pappalardo et al., 1999
8	Gulf of Naples	POINT(14.2559 40.7192)	Arienzo et al., 2009
9	Lago Patria (Naples)	POINT(14.0366 40.9260)	Civetta et al., 1997;Scandone et al., 1991
10	Marina di Cassano (Naples)	POINT(14.3998 40.6385)	Civetta et al., 1997
11	Massaquano (Naples)	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	Rosi et al., 1999
12	Monte Echia (Naples)	POINT(14.2479 40.8312)	Pappalardo et al., 1999
13	Lago Grande di Monticchio	POINT(15.6057 40.9315)	Narcisi, 1996
14	Monticchio (Bagni)	POINT(15.5699 40.9490)	Rosi et al., 1999
15	Monticchio Lakes	POINT (15.6098 40.9319)	Brauer et al., 2000;Fedele et al., 2003
16	Murge Plateau	POINT(16.2833 41.0047)	Giaccio et al., 2008
17	Naples	POINT(14.2080 40.8537)	Orsi et al., 1996
18	Pacognano	POINT(14.4347 40.6484)	Civetta et al., 1997;Rosi et al., 1999
19	Paglicci Cave	POINT(15.6150 41.6541)	Giaccio et al., 2008
20	Pellezzano	POINT(14.7546 40.7249)	Rosi et al., 1999
21	Penta	POINT(14.7979 40.7615)	Rosi et al., 1999
22	Phlegraean Fields	POINT(14.1402 40.8275)	Orsi et al., 1996;Fedele et al., 2003
23	Ponti Rossi (Naples)	POINT(14.2594 40.8731)	Civetta et al., 1997;Giaccio et al., 2008
24	Pozzuoli Bay	POINT(14.0890 40.8215)	Orsi et al., 1996
25	Pucara	POINT(14.6459 40.6783)	Civetta et al., 1997
26	Punta Marmolite	POINT(14.1489 40.8888)	Pappalardo et al., 1999
27	Sant' Agata dei due Golfi	POINT(14.3733 40.6070)	Civetta et al., 1997
28	Sant' Angelo a Scala	POINT(14.7402 40.9746)	Rosi et al., 1999
29	San Marco	POINT(14.3381 41.0369)	Civetta et al., 1997
30	San Nicola La Strada	POINT(14.3313 41.0518)	Civetta et al., 1997

id	label	wkt	literature
31	Scarafea Area	POINT(14.1560 40.9346)	Civetta et al., 1997
32	Serino	POINT(14.8706 40.8567)	Fedele et al., 2008;Giaccio et al.
33	Starza	POINT(14.7567 41.0075)	Rosi et al., 1999
34	Torregaveta	POINT(14.0477 40.8111)	Pappalardo et al., 1999
35	Trefola	POINT(14.1486 40.8926)	Pappalardo et al., 1999
36	Tufara	POINT(14.7069 41.0577)	Rosi et al., 1999
37	Tufarella Area	POINT(14.7906 40.7616)	Rosi et al., 1999
38	Vico Equense	POINT(14.4273 40.6622)	Rosi et al., 1999
39	Villa di Briano (Naples)	POINT(14.1607 41.0000)	Civetta et al., 1997
40	Voscone Area	POINT(14.5194 40.8005)	Rosi et al., 1999

Dates of CI localities in Europe and along the Mediterranean Sea. The localities are sorted by country.

id	label	wkt	literature
41	Lake Ohrid (Albania)	POINT(20.6749 40.9874)	Leicher et al., 2019, 2016
42	Kozarnika Cave (Bulgaria)	POINT(22.7024 43.6519)	Lowe et al., 2012
43	Temnata Cave (Bulgaria)	POINT(23.3848 43.0892)	Fedele et al., 2008, 2003
44	Toplitsa Cave (Bulgaria)	POINT(24.0053 43.1907)	Tsanova et al., 2021
45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	POINT(23.1311 37.4226)	Fedele et al., 2003
46	Klissoura (Greece)	POINT(21.4672 40.5361)	Lowe et al., 2012
47	Tenaghi Philippon (Greece)	POINT(24.2274 40.9794)	Lowe et al., 2012;Wulf et al., 2018
48	Susak Island (Greece)	POINT(14.2921 44.5104)	Wacha, 2011
49	Lake Ohrid (Macedonia)	POINT(20.7409 41.0467)	Leicher et al., 2016,2019
50	Golema Pesht Cave (Macedonia)	POINT(21.1617 41.8117)	Lowe et al., 2012
51	Crvena Stiljena (Montenegro)	POINT(18.4815 42.7790)	Morley & Woodward, 2011
52	Urluia (Romania)	POINT(27.9021 44.0947)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013,2014 Obrecht et al., 2017 Pötter et al., 2021

id	label	wkt	literature
53	Dobrogea (Romania)	POINT(28.2329 43.9996)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013,2014
54	Vlasca (Romania)	POINT(27.8491 44.3921)	Obreht et al., 2017
55	Lower Danube Basin (Romania)	POINT(25.2920 43.6550)	Obreht et al., 2017
56	Bratul Borcea (Romania)	POINT(27.3271 44.1891)	Pötter et al., 2021
57	Balta Alba (Romania)	POINT(27.2478 45.3037)	Pötter et al., 2021
58	Russian Plane	POINT(45.0000 55.0000)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013
59	Kostenki-Borshchevo (Russia)	POINT(39.0517 51.3858)	Fedele et al., 2008;Giaccio et al., 2008
60	Kostenki (Russia)	POINT(39.0473 51.3858)	Fedele et al., 2003
61	Kisiljevo (Serbia)	POINT(21.3912 44.7397)	Baykal et al., 2018
62	Tabula Traiana (Serbia)	POINT(22.3094 44.6568)	Boric et al., 2012;Lowe et al., 2012
63	Titel Plateau (Serbia)	POINT(20.3026 45.2034)	Baykal et al., 2018
64	Southern Ukraine	POINT(31.8000 47.4300)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013
65	Haua-Fteah (Libya)	POINT(22.0516 32.9002)	Lowe et al., 2012

3 MODELLING AS LINKED OPEN DATA

To model and publish all the 'hidden assumptions' behind the georeferencing methods Linked Open Data can be used [12, 13, 9, 2]. For this purpose the "Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology" (fuzzy-sl-ontology) has been created and is currently under development (see <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/fuzzy-sl-ontology>). This ontology is based on PROV-O, SKOS and GeoSPARQL [4]. The PROV-O model defines three basic classes: Entity, Activity and Agent. Transferred to the georeferencing task, the entity is a site (modelled with another GeoSPARQL node), the activity is the method used, and the agent is the person who has done the job. Using this lightweight ontology, the georeferencing task of Uluia can be executed.

The CI sites (near Naples, Fig. 3 and in Europe, Fig. 4) are modelled in a GitHub repository (see <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/campanian-ignimbrite-geo>). In this, the CSV files are tackled by a Python Script, that transforms the data into RDF using the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology. The data is published using the SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation Tool and published via, e.g., https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/Site_collection/index.html.

Figure 3: CI Sites near Naples. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

Figure 4: CI Sites in Europe. Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0.

REFERENCES

- [1] Barberi, F.; Innocenti, F.; Lirer, L.; Munno, R.; Pescatore, T.; Santacroce, R.: The Campanian Ignimbrite: A major prehistoric eruption in the Neapolitan area (Italy). *Bulletin of Volcanology*, 41, 1978.
- [2] Berners-Lee, T.: Linked Data - Design Issues, 2006. <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>.
- [3] Brauer, A.; Mingram, J.; Frank, U.; Günter, C.; Georg Schettler; Wulf, S.; Zolitschka, B.; Negen-dank, J.F.: Abrupt environmental oscillations during the Early Weichselian recorded at Lago Grande di Monticchio, southern Italy. *Quaternary International*, 73-74, 79–90, 2000. ISSN 10406182. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(00\)00066-5](http://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(00)00066-5).
- [4] Car, N.J.; Homburg, T.: GeoSPARQL 1.1: Motivations, Details and Applications of the Decadal Update to the Most Important Geospatial LOD Standard. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 11(2), 117, 2022. ISSN 2220-9964. <http://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi11020117>.
- [5] De Vivo, B.; Rolandi, G.; Gans, P.B.; Calvert, A.; Bohron, W.A.; Spera, F.J.; Belkin, H.E.: New constraints on the pyroclastic eruptive history of the Campanian volcanic Plain (Italy). *Mineralogy and Petrology*, 73(1-3), 47–65, 2001. ISSN 0930-0708, 1438-1168. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s007100170010>.
- [6] Fedele, F.G.; Giaccio, B.; Hajdas, I.: Timescales and cultural process at 40,000 BP in the light of the Campanian Ignimbrite eruption, Western Eurasia. *Journal of Human Evolution*, 55(5), 834–857, 2008. ISSN 00472484. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2008.08.012>.
- [7] Fitzsimmons, K.E.; Hambach, U.: Loess accumulation during the last glacial maximum: Evidence from Urluia, southeastern Romania. *Quaternary International*, 334-335, 74–85, 2014. ISSN 10406182. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2013.08.005>.
- [8] Giaccio, B.; Isaia, R.; Fedele, F.G.; Di Canzio, E.; Hoffecker, J.; Ronchitelli, A.; Sinitsyn, A.A.; Anikovich, M.; Lisitsyn, S.N.; Popov, V.V.: The Campanian Ignimbrite and Codola tephra layers: Two temporal/stratigraphic markers for the Early Upper Palaeolithic in southern Italy and eastern Europe. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 177(1), 208–226, 2008. ISSN 03770273. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2007.10.007>.
- [9] Isaksen, L.: Archaeology and the Semantic Web. Thesis (Doctoral), University of Southampton, School of Electronics and Computer Science, 2011. <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/id/eprint/206421>.
- [10] Marti, A.; Folch, A.; Costa, A.; Engwell, S.: Reconstructing the plinian and co-ignimbrite sources of large volcanic eruptions: A novel approach for the Campanian Ignimbrite. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1), 21220, 2016. ISSN 2045-2322. <http://doi.org/10.1038/srep21220>.
- [11] Orsi, G.; De Vita, S.; Di Vito, M.: The restless, resurgent Campi Flegrei nested caldera (Italy): constraints on its evolution and configuration. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 74(3-4), 179–214, 1996. ISSN 03770273. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0273\(96\)00063-7](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0273(96)00063-7).
- [12] Schmidt, S.C.; Thiery, F.; Trognitz, M.: Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata. *Digital*, 2(3), 333–364, 2022. ISSN 2673-6470. <http://doi.org/10.3390/digital2030019>.
- [13] Thiery, F.: Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Töpferstempel. *Squirrel Papers*, 4(1), No.3, 2013. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.292979>.